

THE PROCESS OF TRADITIONAL FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF CLASSICAL MUSIC

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Abstract: The role of music in human life, music of the past and future, the influence of human scientific achievements on musical processes, today's music and the process of formation of musical processes until now.

Key words: music, religious music, classical, Uzbek classical music, musical heritage, teacher-disciple traditions.

Humanity was created in such a way that before the formation of nation, nation, writing, cultural and even spiritual views, it took part in the awakening of the first buds of music. During the fulfillment of their personal needs (herding animals, hunting, sending messages to each other, even occupying other lands;) unknowingly, the first musical instruments, the first sparks of rhythmic division, started his musical evolution in general.

"Music (from Greek *mousiké* - art of the fairies of inspiration) is the art of sound;

Music (wool *mousiche* - the art of the muses) - a type of art that reflects human emotional experiences, thoughts, imagination through the consistency or set of musical sounds (tones, melodies)."

The development of musical processes is related to the period of human civilization and spirituality. Humanity has experienced various periods and processes during historical changes. Of course, each change has reflected its mark on aspects of lifestyle and cultural life. In particular, art and culture, like all fields, have made their way from the system of the first primitive community millions of years ago to the technologically advanced society of the 21st century.

If we look at history, each renaissance period in the field of art corresponds to another level of increase in science and human intellectual potential. That is, the increase in the level of human knowledge has had an impact on views in every field. Similarly, Uzbek folk music embodies the spiritual maturity of our ancestors, formed over centuries. In particular, Farabi, Ibn Sina, Ibn Zayla, Abu Abdullah Khorezmi and many other encyclopedic scholars paid special attention to the science of music and contributed to the development of the scientific views of ancient scientists and philosophers in a theoretical and practical way. .

"Pharaobi mentions the names and works of Greek thinkers Galen, Pythagoras, Aristotle, Ptolemy, Phimistius in the "Big Book of Music", while Ibn Sina mentions Euclid and his "Book of the Law" and Ptolemy in the "Collection of the Science of Music". Although Ibn Zayla does not mention any of the Greek scholars in the "Complete Book of Music" and Khorezmi in the chapter devoted to music in "The Keys of the Sciences", *نَوْمَكْتَمَلَا* (the ancients) or *نَوْمَقَوْمَلَا* When he writes (musicologist), he means them."

The main link in the development process of musical works is closely connected with folk art, i.e. folklore. The formation of the first musical manifestations is also directly related

to folk art. As the human intellectual capacity increased, his thinking about the environment and the world grew, and he began to think about the reasons for the creation of man and the purpose of living.

In the formation of the first foci of art, culture, and spirituality, the religious views of people performed the main task. Humans believed that every creature, plant, and existence in nature was controlled by a divine power, and they deified images and worshiped them in different forms. Now they have learned to use music or other forms of art not only to satisfy their needs, but also to provide spiritual nourishment. These processes were reflected in the spheres of art and culture as humanity changed and developed.

Although the first musical melodies expressed simple, monodic structures, over the centuries these views became more complicated and served as the basis for the emergence of various genres.

"We know that there are views that pluralism was invented by medieval priests, it is wrong to think that it was invented by church priests. In fact, the church was against polyphony and was forced to accept it only after a hard struggle, under the pressure of musical practice. Some music historians attribute the creation of polyphony to a "chosen" race of great talent. But the elements of polyphony are present in the music of different peoples of the globe."

In the formation of qualities such as high culture, humanity, and patriotism in people, the role of artists and creators is incomparable. Because the society usually follows someone for a certain period of time and promotes some news among themselves. Later, this propaganda becomes a law, a rule, a value, a tradition in that nation or the entire humanity. Musical genres have also been refined and developed over the years and have reached their present form. However, since the current era is the age of technology, the directions and types of musical genres are also increasing. People are gradually moving away from classical music traditions. It is obvious that these genres, which have their own laws and rules, seem too heavy and complicated for the technologically advanced society. The demand of the period is supporting relatively light and fast-paced processes.

Uzbek musical heritage has developed and formed through many historical processes. The preservation of our musical heritage is directly related to the widespread use of the teacher-disciple tradition.

"Fossil monuments found on the territory of Uzbekistan, as well as written sources that have reached us, testify to the great antiquity of the musical heritage of the Uzbek people. The Uzbek musical heritage is diverse in terms of genres, consisting of vocal and instrumental melodies (mostly solo and solo, as well as unison choral and ensemble performances), folklore with a monodic structure, and professional in the oral tradition. includes creations (statues and similar large-scale works of complex form). In connection with the ethnic commonality of the population of Uzbekistan and the socio-economic conditions, the musical heritage of the Uzbek people can be distinguished into 4 main local styles - Khorezm, Bukhara - Samarkand, Fergana - Tashkent, Surkhandarya - Kashkadarya.."

Every direction needs innovation, rebirth. Including new directions and methods in musical genres are also unique. It is also a sad fact that certain types of "modern" styles created in line with our time have a negative effect on the consciousness of the society. Because we cannot control the news and changes without knowing how and where the existence around us came from.

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